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D13.2 Dissemination and Communication activities report (first version)

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
JRAs	Joint Research Activities
N/A	Not Applicable
WP	Work Package
TA	Transnational Access

Abstract

The dissemination and communication of the VITALISE project activities, advances and results play a crucial role for the overall success of the project. They set the ground for future exploitation and sustainability of the project results and develop a clear understanding of the value stemming from the project outputs. This document, D13.2 “Dissemination and Communication activities report (first version)”, aims to detail all the dissemination, communication and outreach activities that have been implemented within the VITALISE Project from M1 until M18.

As described in D13.1 “Dissemination and Communication Plan” which elaborates on the dissemination and communication strategy of the VITALISE project, the consortium partners engage in several dissemination and communication activities throughout the project to ensure the visibility, dissemination and exploitation of the findings of VITALISE across the project’s target groups. In order for the dissemination planning and methodology to be effective, a co-designed programme of activities has been implemented, based on the profiles of the target audiences, highlighting the benefits and results delivered to stakeholders, and ensuring their active involvement in the activities of the project. These activities include workshops, networking events, conferences, training sessions, press releases, newsletters, scientific publications, social media posts and more and they are presented in detail in the following chapters.

1 Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g., healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in-person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 Description of WP13 “Dissemination, Exploitation, Openness and Sustainability”

The “WP13 Dissemination, Exploitation, Openness and Sustainability” describes all the dissemination and communication activities that will take place throughout the project aiming to maximize its impact and ensure the visibility, dissemination and exploitation of the progress and findings of VITALISE across the project target groups and audiences. This deliverable provides details on how the consortium identifies, mobilises and engages with stakeholder groups.

Overall, the objectives of WP13 are:

- To raise awareness within participants, target groups and the European society at large about the existence of VITALISE, its objectives, progress and results.
- To ensure that the project’s results reach the various target groups and the European Society, thus stimulating a dialogue about Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.
- To update stakeholders with news and improvements related to VITALISE.
- To plan and verify the exploitation potential and added value of all the VITALISE exploitable outcomes during and beyond the end of the project progress.
- To co-design and co-develop sustainable business models out of the main VITALISE project results that will target on the sustainability of VITALISE after the end of the project.

1.3 Purpose and Scope

This document, D13.2 “Dissemination and Communication activities report (first version)”, aims to detail all the dissemination, communication and outreach activities that have been implemented within the VITALISE Project from M1 until M18. As described in D13.1 “Dissemination and Communication Plan” which elaborates on the dissemination and communication strategy of VITALISE project, the consortium partners engage in several activities throughout the project to ensure the visibility, dissemination and exploitation of the VITALISE findings across the project’s target groups. To this end, the VITALISE partners have carried out a co-designed programme of activities, in order to highlight the benefits and results delivered to stakeholders and ensure their

active involvement in the activities of the project. These activities included workshops, networking events, conferences, training sessions, press releases, newsletters, scientific publications, social media posts and more.

The main objectives of the VITALISE dissemination and communication strategy are the following:

- **Engagement of stakeholders:** VITALISE aims to engage with bodies of third parties which act as contributors to the development, evaluation, uptake and exploitation of the project's outcomes and encourages their participation in the project's activities in a systematic way.
- **Awareness building:** To ensure a certain level of impact and promote a European collaborative approach on research and innovation, it is crucial for VITALISE to work towards the cultivation of awareness in diverse target audience environments.
- **Feedback extraction:** As VITALISE is a multidisciplinary project, it is expected to produce several reports and tools. It is purposeful to disseminate such materials towards target audiences that will grasp knowledge and provide valuable and critical insights.
- **Collaboration:** As VITALISE is operating in a cross-European and multidisciplinary level, there are multiple entities which would be of high influence on the project in terms of creating a network of organisations that operate on the same level and domain.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

D13.2 "Dissemination and Communication activities report (first version)" discusses and analyses the dissemination and communication activities implemented within the project from its very beginning until M18. The deliverable involves four chapters:

- The **first chapter** is introductory, aiming to provide the context, purpose and scope of the document.
- The **second chapter** describes the dissemination reporting process of the VITALISE project and the dedicated online reporting tool.
- The **third chapter** includes a detailed report of all the dissemination and communication activities that took place within the VITALISE project from M1 until M18.
- The **fourth chapter** is a summary of the performance and outreach achieved through the dissemination activities that were implemented in the project.

1.5 Relation to other WPs and tasks

The broader goal of the dissemination and communication strategy of VITALISE is to raise awareness in diverse environments and ensure that the results are leveraged by the identified stakeholder groups. Hence, the overall project Dissemination and Communication Plan is directly associated with the outcomes of the different WPs in the project since they feed useful content to be disseminated from the partnership.

Figure 1 depicts the VITALISE project methodology and workplan. The scheme demonstrates the horizontal interaction of "WP13 Dissemination, Exploitation, Openness and Sustainability" with the rest of the WPs of the project. Therefore, the dissemination and communication activities support all project activities that take place within the context of other work packages.

Figure 1 Project Methodology and Work Plan

2 Dissemination Reporting Process

2.1 Purpose of the reporting process

This section describes the process followed by the VITALISE partners in order to report their dissemination and communication activities. Dissemination activities are essential for the impact maximisation, visibility and exploitation of the progress and findings of VITALISE across the project target groups and audiences. What is more, dissemination and communication of the project results are contractual obligations stated in project's Grant Agreement, and specifically in Articles 29.1 and 38.1.1. For this reason, all the VITALISE partners make sure to engage in dissemination and communication activities and keep track of all these activities and their outreach and performance.

2.2 About the VITALISE Dissemination Activities Reporting Tool

The VITALISE Dissemination Activities Reporting is an online tool used by all the consortium partners to report and keep track of the dissemination and communication activities that have been implemented throughout the project. The dissemination reporting tool is available online and can be accessed through the following [link](#).

All the VITALISE consortium partners have to report any dissemination and communication activity they implement to the online reporting tool. The types of dissemination activities that VITALISE partners could potentially engage with are:

- Organisation of a Workshop or a Networking event
- Participation to a Workshop
- Participation to a Conference
- Participation to an Event, other than a Conference or a Workshop (Networking events, Exhibitions, Symposia, Webinars etc.)
- Participation in activities, organized jointly with other H2020 projects (Liaison Synergies)
- Training Session
- Press release
- Newsletter
- Scientific and peer reviewed publication (article and/or papers and/or presentation)
- Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication) (Blog entries)
- Media Publications (News pieces, articles etc.)
- Poster
- Flyer
- Social Media
- Website
- Video/Film

- Other

The dissemination reporting is an internal process among the consortium partners, employed to feed the project website with information about the reported activities, share the reported information through the VITALISE social media and analyse the information to extract statistics and conclusions about the progress and performance of the dissemination and communication strategy of the project. A snapshot of the current form of the VITALISE Dissemination Activities Reporting tool is available in Annex 14 "The VITALISE Dissemination Activities Reporting Tool".

3 Dissemination and Communication Activities Report

This section of the document reports all the dissemination and communication activities that were implemented within VITALISE from M1 until M18 of the project.

3.1 Visual Identity

From M1 until M3 of the project, communication efforts focused on building the branding and visual identity of the VITALISE Project. To this end, several communication artefacts, materials, templates and the project logo were developed.

3.1.1 Logo

The VITALISE project logo (Figure 2) ensures the recognition of the project among all target audiences and it is used in all the dissemination materials, documents, presentations, etc. in a prominent way.

Figure 2 VITALISE Logo (Vertical and Horizontal)

More information about the concept behind the project logo are available in D13.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan.

3.1.2 Document and presentation templates

Clean and functional document and presentation templates were developed in the beginning of the project to maintain coherence among the many different documents produced. Those templates include a deliverable and document template, as well as a presentation template, as seen in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3 VITALISE Presentations Template

D13.2 Dissemination and Communication activities report (first version)

Figure 4 VITALISE Documents Template

3.1.3 Brochures, flyers, posters

From M1 until M18 of the project, several posters, brochures and flyers were developed, to communicate the purpose and scope of the project, as well as its diverse activities. All these materials are uploaded on the VITALISE website in this [link](#). The official poster of the project is also available in Annex 11 “The Poster of VITALISE Project” while the brochure of the project is available in Annex 12 “The Brochure of VITALISE Project”. In addition, throughout the document, several posters and banners, prepared for the different activities of the project, are displayed.

3.1.4 Project presentation

An overall project presentation of VITALISE was created and uploaded in this [link](#), in order to present the project goals, objectives and roadmap. The VITALISE project presentation includes all the important information that create a clear understanding of project’s challenges, impact, concept, activities, procedures and expected results (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Slides from the VITALISE project presentation

In several instances, presentations regarding specific activities of the project were also developed. For example, through this [link](#), the VITALISE website visitors can download a full presentation of the project’s Joint Research Activities (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Slides from the Joint Research Activities Presentation

3.2 The VITALISE Project Website

3.2.1 About the Website

Figure 7 Snapshot of the VITALISE Project's Website Homepage

3.2.2 Structure of the Website and Main Sections

As previously mentioned, as the project progresses, new content is constantly uploaded on the VITALISE website, to keep visitors up to date with the project advances. Currently, the VITALISE website consists of **46 posts** and **83 pages**. The current structure of the VITALISE website homepage is depicted in Figure 8.

One of the most crucial tools for the successful dissemination and communication of the results of VITALISE is the project website, whose first version launched on the first month (M1) of its lifecycle (April 2021). The current look of the VITALISE website's homepage is available in Figure 7. The website domain name is <https://vitalise-project.eu>. All the necessary information regarding the progress of the project as well as project news, materials, etc. are uploaded on the project website.

In particular, the VITALISE website aims to:

- Provide information about the project, its main objectives, description of the produced outputs and knowledge, publications, latest news and upcoming events in which VITALISE participates, information about project partners with a link to their websites, subscription to the project newsletter, social networks and contact information.
- Communicate the actual value stemming from the project to all the stakeholder groups, so as to encourage their active involvement and participation in project's activities.

The website is the project's main portal for communicating its outputs and results with its target audiences. For this reason, it is frequently updated with new content and adjusted according to the project's advancements and results.

Why VITALISE	Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures	Harmonisation Board	Summer Schools	Open Access to research data	Scientific Publications	News
Objectives and Outcomes	Virtual Access to Datasets selected during the JRAs	Harmonisation Body	Learning Lab Day 0 & Commercialisation Bootcamp		Deliverables	Events
Workplan	Joint Research Activities (JRAs)	Harmonisation Wiki				Newsletter
Methodology	Infrastructure					Media Gallery
Consortium						

Figure 8 Structure of the VITALISE Website

The main sections of the website are:

- **Access to infrastructure:** In this section website visitors can access all the necessary information regarding applying for Transnational Access to the Research Infrastructures of VITALISE Project, along with detailed descriptions of each infrastructure, the application process and opportunities for Joint Research Activities (JRAs). The section also includes information about getting Virtual Access to the datasets of the project selected during the JRAs.
- **Harmonisation:** This section is dedicated to informing website visitors about the methodology followed within the project in order to create a harmonized framework for Health & Wellbeing Living Labs, as well as how all individuals interested in the Living Lab offerings and methodologies can get involved in the process.
- **Capacity Building and Training:** This section is dedicated to informing all website visitors about the capacity building and training opportunities that the VITALISE Project offers, regarding Living Lab tools and methodologies.
- **ICT tools:** This section has some preliminary information about the ICT Tools that are being developed within the framework of the VITALISE Project in order to provide open access to research data to external researchers.
- **Publications:** All deliverables and scientific publications produced within VITALISE Project are published in the “Publications” section.
- **Press:** In this section all the news, events, newsletters and media materials produced within the VITALISE Project are openly published to be accessible by the public.

3.2.3 Blog Posts and News Items

As mentioned above, the VITALISE website currently has a number of 46 posts. These posts are news items and blogposts published in the “News” section of the website, including the latest news and updates stemming from the project.

Figure 9 Snapshot from the "News" Section

The “News” section can be accessed through this [link](#).

3.2.4 Performance and Outreach

The VITALISE website significantly contributes to the dissemination of key messages produced in the project, reaching a broad audience of stakeholders on a daily basis. From M1 until M18, the project website had more than 7.2k users who on average engaged with website’s content for 1’ and 32”. As seen in Figure 10 the visits on the website peaked during the first Open Call for Transnational Access.

Figure 10 Analytics of the VITALISE website (M1-M18)

As the main communication tool of VITALISE, the project website will continue to be frequently updated, so that new content reaches the target audiences. The consortium partners play a key role in this process, since they contribute photos, videos and reports from all the VITALISE-related activities to be used in publicity materials.

3.3 Social Media

3.3.1 About the VITALISE Social Media accounts

VITALISE project’s social media channels are a much-needed part of its dissemination and communication strategy, since they allow engaging stakeholders with the project activities and news, while creating a space where interaction is enabled, as well as discussions and provision of feedback. Through the use of social media, VITALISE manages to build a steady flow of information towards diverse audiences and sustain a well-informed group of target audiences, which enhances project’s overall impact.

Through Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and YouTube, information about the project status and activities are made available to the public. The links of the VITALISE social media channels are the following:

- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/VITALISEproject>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/vitalise-project/>
- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/VITALISEproject>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCTvXvgIRLL29-3d9LTulq3A>

Figure 11 Examples of posts on the VITALISE Social Media accounts

The use of the right social media channels to communicate and disseminate messages regarding the project can significantly help VITALISE increase its reach. In the chapters to follow, the outreach achieved through the social media accounts of the VITALISE project will be reviewed.

3.3.2 Facebook

Facebook is an online social media platform with more than 2.93 billion monthly active users, providing a very broad audience to reach out to. Ranked as the third most visited websites worldwide as of July 2022, it comes as no surprise that through Facebook, VITALISE managed to reach more than **10k user views** until M18 of the project.

Figure 12 VITALISE Facebook page analytics (M1-M18)

Currently, VITALISE has **186 followers** on Facebook and **153 posts** in total.

3.3.3 Twitter

Twitter is a micro-blogging social media platform and stands among the most popular ones available on the internet. Even though compared to Facebook and other platforms it counts less users, Twitter’s audience is plugged-in, receptive, and dynamic, which enables the broadcast of messages to a captive audience more easily. Until M18, VITALISE has achieved approximately **75k impressions** on Twitter, as seen in Figure 13.

Figure 13 VITALISE Project Twitter Impressions (M1-M18)

Currently, VITALISE has **229 followers** on Twitter and **142 posts**.

3.3.4 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is an online Social Media Platform that allows for targeted outreach to audiences with specific professional interests. Through LinkedIn, VITALISE managed to reach approximately **47k user views** until M18 of the project.

Figure 14 VITALISE LinkedIn Impressions (M6-M18)

Currently, VITALISE has **575 followers** on LinkedIn and **113 posts** in total.

3.3.5 YouTube

Video content production can be a powerful tool to spread a message in a pertinent and easy to understand manner to a wider audience. For this reason, VITALISE regularly produces video content and shares it on its [YouTube channel](#) and other social media pages.

Figure 15 The VITALISE YouTube Channel

Currently, 7 videos have been uploaded on the VITALISE YouTube Channel, counting more than **575 views** in total.

3.3.6 Posts on partners' social media

All project partners in VITALISE use their own social media platforms to post about the results and activities of the project, acting as essential multipliers for the outreach of the project. Multipliers are social media channels that could potentially facilitate the direct engagement with more users and thus, enable the dissemination of content such as articles, photos and videos to a broader audience, while simultaneously assisting the creation of brand affinity. This process significantly facilitates the growth of the VITALISE community and fosters stakeholder engagement.

Figure 16 Examples of Social Media Posts by VITALISE Partners

A full list of the reported social media posts of the VITALISE partners from M1 until M18 has been included in Table 5 List of Partners' social media posts and outreach.

3.4 Media Publications (News pieces, articles etc.)

Other than social media posts, until M18 the VITALISE partners have generated several media publications, both in English and their own languages, to disclose information about the project, its news and activities. The full list of Media Publications produced until M18 is shown in Table 1 Media Publications about VITALISE.

Table 1 Media Publications about VITALISE

Media Publications				
Date	Partner	Title	Medium	URL
31/3/21	INTRAS	VITALISE, the European project at the service of Living Lab harmonization that shows us the importance of empathy (original: <i>VITALISE, el proyecto europeo al servicio de la armonización Living Lab que nos marca la importancia de la empatía</i>)	Fundacion Intras website	Link
14/4/21	TREBA G	VITALISE	Trebag website	Link
26/4/21	SIT	VITALISE: the launch of the new H2020 project	SocialIT website	Link
27/4/21	N/A	VITALISE Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure	RRI Tools website	Link
29/4/21	LICALA B	VITALISE: harmonization of procedures for living labs in the field of health and well-being (original: <i>VITALISE: harmonisatie van</i>)	LiCalab website	Link

		<i>procedures voor proeftuinen in het domein van gezondheid en welzijn)</i>		
30/4/21	UPM	Virtual health and wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure	LifeSTech website	Link
30/4/21	INTRAS	Starts H2020 VITALISE project of harmonization and virtual infrastructure of Living Labs of health and well-being	Fundacion Intras website	Link
1/5/21	AV	VITALISE	Anthology Ventures website	Link
31/5/21	LICALA B	Vitalise-horizon-2020	LiCalab website	Link
1/6/21	SIT	Information about the Vitalise project	SocialIT website	Link
17/6/21	TREBAG	Participation in two Horizon 2020 project consortia (original: <i>Két Horizon 2020 projekt konzorciumban vezsünk részt</i>)	TREBAG	Link
30/6/21	VILABS	VITALISE	VR4REHAB online library	Link
22/9/21	ENoLL	Receive the latest news from VITALISE project	ENoLL website	Link
29/9/21	ENoLL	Everyone is welcome to join the VITALISE Harmonization Body for Living Labs	ENoLL website	Link
31/1/22	LICALA B	H2020-project Vitalise publiceert twee use cases	LiCalab website	Link
9/2/22	INTRAS	VITALISE	Fundacion Intras website	Link
31/3/22	LICALA B	[Vitalise] Rehabilitation Supported by Technology: Protocol for an International Co-Creation and User Experience Study (original: <i>[Vitalise] Revalidatie Ondersteund door Technologie: Protocol voor een internationaal 'co-creatie en gebruikerservaring'-onderzoek</i>)	LiCalab website	Link
31/5/22	LICALA B	Vitalise: partners meet in Finland (original: <i>Vitalise: partners ontmoeten elkaar in Finland</i>)	LiCalab website	Link

3.5 Press Releases

In the first 18 months of the project, several Press Releases have been produced about the news of the VITALISE Project, both in English and in partner languages, and disseminated through different platforms and media. The full list of the Press Releases produced until M18 is available in Table 2 Press Releases about VITALISE.

Table 2 Press Releases about VITALISE

Press Releases				
Date	Partner	Title	Medium	URL

19/4/21	AUTH	Transfer of know-how and access to new researchers to the Living Lab research infrastructures of AUTH (original: <i>Μεταφορά τεχνογνωσίας και πρόσβαση νέων ερευνητών στις ερευνητικές υποδομές των "Ζωντανών Εργαστηρίων" του ΑΠΘ</i>)	Athenian-Macedonian News Agency	Link
1/6/21	VILABS	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure H2020 VITALISE project kicked off	CORDIS EU	Link
1/3/22	VILABS	Transnational Access to the RIs of VITALISE Project - Info Days	CORDIS EU	Link
1/3/22	VILABS	Apply for free access to the Research Infrastructures of the European VITALISE Project (original: <i>Κάντε Αίτηση για Δωρεάν Πρόσβαση στις Ερευνητικές Υποδομές του Ευρωπαϊκού Έργου VITALISE</i>)	Eduguide	Link
10/3/22	TUE	The kick-off of VITALISE Project (Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure) (original: <i>Start VITALISE met Virtuele Gezondheid en Welzijn Living Lab Infrastructuur</i>)	SlimmerLeven	Link

3.6 Newsletters

3.6.1 VITALISE Newsletters

Figure 17 Snapshot from VITALISE Newsletter #2

3.6.1.1 VITALISE Newsletter #01

The first VITALISE Newsletter circulated on M6 (September 2021) of the project, with the aim to introduce the project and inform the community about its news and advances.

VITALISE Newsletter #01 reached more than 50 recipients. The full newsletter can be accessed through this [link](#).

3.6.1.2 VITALISE Newsletter #02

The second VITALISE Newsletter was released on M12 of the project (March 2022) with the aim to inform "VITALISers" about news, Open Calls and event participation opportunities.

VITALISE Newsletter #02 reached approx. 100 recipients and the full item is available in this [link](#).

3.6.1.3 Communications with the Harmonisation Body

The VITALISE Harmonisation Body is a community of individuals interested in the Living Lab offerings and methodologies that works towards the creation of a harmonized framework and common language for providing Living Lab services. VITALISE has been contacting the Harmonisation Body through a dedicated mailing list, in order to invite the community to participate in open harmonisation events and especially the Harmonisation Board and Body Meetings that take place every 6 months.

Some of the communications addressed to the Harmonisation Body through this dedicated mailing list are listed below:

- First Harmonisation Body meeting: [Link](#)
- Second Harmonisation Body meeting: [Link](#)
- Harmonisation Body Questionnaire: [Link](#)

Figure 18 Snapshots from communications with the Harmonisation Body

3.6.1.4 Communications about Open Calls

VITALISE has created a community and dedicated mailing list consisting of external researchers interested in the Open Calls of the project. When new Open Calls launch within the project, a new message is sent to this community to inform them about opportunities to participate in different project activities.

Some of the communications addressed to the researchers' community interested in the Open Calls of the project, can be accessed through the links below:

- External evaluators Open Call: [Link](#)
- Info Day 1 | Transnational Access: [Link](#)
- Info Day 2 | TA Application Process: [Link](#)

Figure 19 Snapshots from communications about the Open Calls of the project

3.6.2 VITALISE Featured in Partner Newsletters

Other than the newsletters produced within the framework of the VITALISE Project, the consortium partners have also been including news about VITALISE in their organisations' and networks' newsletters. The full list of features of the VITALISE Project in external newsletters is available in Table 3.

Figure 20 The VITALISE Summer School featured in LiCalab's Newsletter

Table 3 VITALISE news included in partner newsletter

VITALISE featured in partners' newsletters			
Date	Partner	Title	URL
28/6/21	LICALAB	Vitalise: 19 European living labs are building living lab standards and procedures (original: <i>Vitalise: 19 Europese living labs bouwen aan living lab standaarden en procedures</i>)	Link
20/12/21	LICALAB	Vitalise: help us improve our wiki page (original: <i>Vitalise: help onze wiki-pagina te verbeteren</i>)	Link
31/1/21	LICALAB	Vitalise: use cases about transition of acute care (original: <i>Vitalise: use cases over transitie van acute zorg</i>)	Link
1/2/22	AUTH	Our News – Issue 10 (original: <i>Τα Νέα μας - Τεύχος 10</i>)	Link
1/3/22	AUTH	Our News – Issue 11 (original: <i>Τα Νέα μας - Τεύχος 11</i>)	Link
31/3/22	LICALAB	Vitalise makes its infrastructure available for transnational access (original: <i>Vitalise stelt infrastructuur ter beschikking voor transnationaal onderzoek</i>)	Link
28/4/22	LICALAB	Vitalise organizes a Summer School in Greece (original: <i>Vitalise organiseert Summer School in Griekenland</i>)	Link
14/6/22	AUTH	Our News – Issue 14 (original: <i>Τα Νέα μας - Τεύχος 14</i>)	Link

3.7 Scientific Publications

VITALISE partners are devoted to the creation of scientific articles, published in the international scientific literature, when possible. All partners acknowledge their common interest in publishing the knowledge to obtain recognition and to advance the state of knowledge in the field. All scientific publications published within the framework of the VITALISE Project are available on the project website in this [link](#), while a full list has also been included in Table 4 of this deliverable.

Table 4 Scientific Publications produced within VITALISE

Scientific Publications produced within VITALISE				
Date	Name	Citation	Publisher	Link
6/1/22	Cocreating a Harmonized Living Lab for Big Data–Driven Hybrid Persona Development: Protocol for Cocreating, Testing, and Seeking Consensus	Santonen T, Petsani D, Julin M, Garschall M, Kropf J, Van der Auwera V, Bernaerts S, Losada R, Almeida R, Garatea J, Muñoz I, Nagy E, Kehayia E, de Guise E, Nadeau S, Azevedo N, Segkouli S, Lazarou I, Petronikolou V, Bamidis P, Konstantinidis E. (2022). Cocreating a Harmonized Living Lab for Big Data–Driven Hybrid Persona Development: Protocol for Cocreating, Testing, and Seeking Consensus. <i>JMIR Res Protoc</i> 2022;11(1):e34567, doi: 10.2196/34567 PMID: 34989697	JMIR Research Protocols	Link
19/1/22	Digital Biomarkers for Supporting Transitional Care Decisions: Protocol for a	Petsani D, Ahmed S, Petronikolou V, Kehayia E, Alastalo M, Santonen T, Merino-Barbancho B, Cea G, Segkouli S, Stavropoulos T, Billis A, Doumas M, Almeida R, Nagy E, Broeckx L, Bamidis P, Konstantinidis E. (2022). Digital Biomarkers for Supporting Transitional Care Decisions:	JMIR Research Protocols	Link

	Transnational Feasibility Study	Protocol for a Transnational Feasibility Study, JMIR Res Protoc 2022;11(1):e34573. URL:https://www.researchprotocols.org/2022/1/e34573, DOI: 10.2196/34573		
9/3/22	Incorporation of Synthetic Data Generation Techniques within a Controlled Data Processing Workflow in the Health and Wellbeing Domain	Hernandez, M., Epelde, G., Beristain, A., Álvarez, R., Molina, C., Larrea, X., Alberdi, A., Timoleon, M., Bamidis, P., Konstantinidis, E. Incorporation of Synthetic Data Generation Techniques within a Controlled Data Processing Workflow in the Health and Wellbeing Domain. Electronics. 2022; 11(5):812. https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics11050812	MDPI	Link
10/3/2022	Rehabilitation Supported by Technology: Protocol for an International Cocreation and User Experience Study	Bernaerts S, De Witte NAJ, Van der Auwera V, Bonroy B, Muraru L, Bamidis P, Frantzidis C, Kourtidou-Papadeli C, Azevedo N, Gareatea J, Muñoz I, Almeida R, Losada R, Fung J, Kehayia E, Lamontagne A, de Guise E, Duclos C, Higgins J, Nadeau S, Beaudry L, Konstantinidis on behalf of the VITALISE consortium. Rehabilitation supported by technology: Protocol for an international co-creation and user experience study. JMIR Research Protocols. doi: 10.2196/34537	JMIR Research Protocols	Link
5/6/22	Towards a taxonomy for health living lab data collection devices	Petsani, D., Santonen, T., Konstantinidis, E., Enriquez, L., Petronikolou, V., Maga, C., Makroglou, S., & Bamidis, P. (2022). Towards a taxonomy for health living lab data collection devices. XXXIII ISPIM Innovation Conference “Innovating in a Digital World”.	XXXIII ISPIM Innovation Conference Proceedings	Link
5/6/22	Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs: a standardized evaluation framework	Vervoort, K., Konstantinidis, E., Santonen, T., Petsani, D., Servais, D., De Boer, D., Spagnoli, F., Onur, O., Bertolin, J., Trousse, B., Desole, M., & Bamidis, P. (2022). Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs: a standardized evaluation framework. XXXIII ISPIM Innovation Conference “Innovating in a Digital World”.	XXXIII ISPIM Innovation Conference Proceedings	Link
21/6/22	Synthetic Subject Generation with Coupled Coherent Time Series Data	Larrea, X., Hernandez, M., Epelde, G., Beristain, A., Molina, C., Alberdi, A., Rankin, D., Bamidis, P., Konstantinidis, E. Synthetic Subject Generation with Coupled Coherent Time Series Data. Eng. Proc. 2022, 18, 7. https://doi.org/10.3390/engproc2022018007	MDPI	Link

3.8 Open Calls

3.8.1 Harmonisation Body (August – September 2021)

Figure 21 Banners of the Harmonisation Body Open Call

In August 2021, VITALISE launched its ongoing Open Call for Harmonisation Body members, published on the project website in this [link](#). Through the Open Call, VITALISE invited all individuals interested in the Living Lab offerings and methodologies to register to an online community, where they will be receiving communications about upcoming Harmonisation Board and Body Meetings (approx. 3 hours/6 months) to discuss about the next Standard Version for Living Lab procedures and services and share valuable knowledge with the community.

Figure 22 Harmonisation Body dissemination instances on social media

The Open Call was disseminated both through the online channels (website, social media) of the VITALISE project as well as through the channels of the VITALISE partners. As a result, up to this moment, **61 people** have joined the Harmonisation Body for Living Labs.

3.8.1.1 Living Lab Harmonisation Wiki Forum

Within the framework of its harmonisation activities, VITALISE also created a Living Lab Harmonisation Wiki that is available in this [link](#). The aim of the wiki is to guide Living Lab operators and researchers to execute, develop and maintain a harmonized framework for systematic Living Lab practices (more information available in this [link](#)).

Figure 23 Snapshot from the homepage of the Living Lab Harmonisation Wiki

The Wiki was presented during the first VITALISE Plenary Meeting on 30 November 2021, in the slot dedicated to the first Harmonisation Body Meeting. The video recording is available on the VITALISE YouTube Channels in this [link](#) (from 1:07:41 on).

3.8.2 Harmonisation Board (November 2021)

In November 2021, VITALISE launched an Open Call inviting external Living Lab and harmonisation experts to submit their applications to join the VITALISE Harmonisation Board, a group consisting of representatives of the VITALISE Consortium, as well as external Living Lab and harmonisation experts that will work in collaboration with the Harmonisation Body to define the next Standard Version for Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.

Figure 24 Banner and Social Media announcement of the Harmonisation Board Open Call

Information about the VITALISE Harmonisation Board scope, purpose and members profiles can be found in this [link](#).

Through the evaluation process, eight external experts, with extensive experience on the subject, were invited to join the Harmonisation Board along with another 12 experts of the VITALISE Consortium. A video introduction of the external Harmonisation Board Experts is available in this [link](#).

3.8.3 External evaluators for Transnational Access Research Proposals (March 2022)

In March 2022, VITALISE launched an Open Call for external evaluators that would be responsible for the scientific evaluation of the research proposals submitted for Transnational Access to the Living Labs of VITALISE Project. The Open Call is available in this [link](#).

Figure 25 Banner of the Open Call for External Evaluators

The external evaluators selected through this process are responsible for the evaluation and rating of the research proposals based on the information provided in the application form by the applicants through a process indicated by the VITALISE partners.

3.8.4 First Open Call for Transnational Access

VITALISE launched its first Open Call for Transnational Access to the Living Labs of the project on 1 March 2022. All the necessary information were published on the project’s website in this [link](#). The dissemination and communication of the Open Call was essential for its overall success, hence all project partners engaged in several activities to ensure maximum outreach to all target audiences.

3.8.4.1 Communication materials

Figure 26 Examples of banners created to promote the Open Calls

In order to support the Open Calls’ communication activities, a set of flyers, brochures and posters were created. The aim of these materials was to communicate important information to the target audiences in a concise and attractive manner.

Figure 27 Poster for the First Open Call for TA

3.8.4.2 Website Content and Social Media Outreach

For the purposes of the first Open Call, several pieces of content were published on the project’s website, such as:

- A detailed description of the Living Lab Research Infrastructures of VITALISE Project that are available for Transnational Access.
- A description of the Joint Research Activities (JRAs)
- Guiding tables to help potential applicants find the right Living Lab according to their research needs.
- An online Application Manual
- A FAQs section
- An Application Template
- A mechanism with the Research Infrastructure Leaders contacts for immediate support to the applicants
- News items about Open Call related matters

Figure 28 Snapshots from the descriptions of the Living Labs on the VITALISE website

All the website content was also additionally published in project’s social media channels to increase the outreach of these messages.

3.9 Organisation of Workshops and Networking events

3.9.1 Kick-off meeting open sessions (20 April 2021)

On 20 April 2021 from 12:30-17:30 CEST the VITALISE Project hosted its Kick-off Meeting. Selective sessions were open to the public, so that the community could get to know more about VITALISE and get informed about project activities that are relevant to them. The sessions were livestreamed on project's [YouTube Channel](#) and website.

Figure 29 Snapshots from the VITALISE Project's Kick-Off Meeting

The Open Sessions started with a presentation of the project and the EU's vision for Research Infrastructures in the Health and Wellbeing domain. Then project partners presented the VITALISE Joint Research Activities (JRAs) and Open Calls, the project's Living Lab Research Infrastructures and the work to be implemented for the harmonisation of Living Lab services and procedures. From 15:30 until 16:30 CEST, a round-table discussion on "Health, well-being and socially inclusive cities" took place, moderated by Ugo Guarnacci, Project Adviser at EREA (European Commission) and a panel consisting of:

- Maria Yeroyanni - Senior Expert Innovating Cities, DG R&I, European Commission
- Maria Vasile - Scientific Project Adviser, HADEA, European Commission
- Prof. Leonidas Pavlidis - School of Medicine, University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)
- Prof. Denia Kolokotsa - Technical University of Crete Kounoupidiana, Coordinator of H2020 Varcities
- Prof. Marina Della Giusta - University of Reading, H2020 project IN-HABIT

The Open Sessions ended with a presentation of the capacity building activities and educational material to be implemented in the project.

The event's agenda is available at Appendix 1 "Kick-Off Meeting Agenda", while the full recorded session can be found in this [link](#).

3.9.2 "Establishment of Evaluation Processes and Tools" Workshop (1 June 2021)

On the 1st of June 2021, VITALISE hosted an open to the public workshop, inviting participants to contribute to an open discussion about common ways to evaluate the processes and tools of Health & Wellbeing Living Labs and facilitate harmonisation.

Figure 30 Snapshots from the workshop on "Evaluation Processes & Tools"

The event’s full agenda is available at Annex 2 “Establishment of Evaluation Processes & Tools” Workshop Agenda, and more information about the session can be found in this [link](#).

3.9.3 “Harmonisation of Living Lab Services Terminology” Workshop (1 July 2021)

On the 1st of July 2021, VITALISE Project hosted an online workshop on the “Harmonisation of Living Lab Services Terminology”, inviting every individual interested in the Living Lab offerings and methodologies to contribute to the creation of an initial version of harmonised processes, including a common template to describe Living Lab services and communicate their outcomes in a clear and effective way. The workshop also aimed to raise awareness among participants about the work implemented in the project for the harmonization of Living Lab services and tools and attract some of the participants to join the Harmonisation Body. More information about the event can be found in this [link](#).

Figure 31 Snapshots from the "Harmonisation of Living Lab Services Terminology" Workshop

The workshop’s agenda is available at Annex 3 “Harmonisation of Living Lab Services Terminology” Workshop, while the full recorded session can be found on the VITALISE YouTube Channel in this [link](#).

3.9.4 “VITALISE Technology Demonstrations” Open Session (2 July 2021)

On July 2, 2021, VITALISE invited everyone to join an open session regarding the project’s Technology Demonstrations and find out more about the identified hardware and software examples that are widely used in the majority of pilot studies running in the Health and Wellbeing domain across Europe. The technologies presented were Gradior Cognitive and Gradior Multisensorial Software, Interable prototype – Gradior Physical, CAPTAIN, AgeWell digital coach and MentorAge. More information about this session are available in this [link](#).

Figure 32 Snapshots from the "Technology Demonstrations" Open Session

The open session’s agenda is available in this [link](#), while the full session was recorded and uploaded on the VITALISE YouTube Channel in this [link](#).

3.9.5 VITALISE Plenary Meeting Open Sessions (30 November 2021)

On November 30, 2021, during the VITALISE Project Plenary Meeting, project partners hosted five sessions that were open to the public. The aim of the sessions was to disclose more information about the project’s JRAs and pilots and collaborate on Living Lab labelling and ICT tools requirements. What is more, within this Plenary Meeting, the first Harmonisation Body Meeting took place (More information available at 2.9.6 First Harmonisation Body Meeting (30 November 2021))

Figure 33 Snapshots from the Plenary Meeting on 30 November 2021

More information about this event can be found in this [link](#), while the full session is available on the VITALISE YouTube Channel in this [link](#).

3.9.6 First Harmonisation Body Meeting (30 November 2021)

As mentioned in the previous chapter, the first VITALISE Harmonisation Body Meeting took place within the framework of the project’s first Plenary Meeting on the 30th of November 2021. During the meeting, the Harmonisation Body got to know more about the harmonisation methodology, the Living Lab Management system, the new Wiki Page created to guide Living Lab operators and researchers to execute, develop and maintain a harmonized framework for systematic Living Lab practices, the structure of R&D services information and the real-time wiki testing.

Figure 34 Snapshots from the 1st VITALISE Harmonisation Body Meeting

The full session was recorded and is available on the VITALISE YouTube Channel in this [link](#) from [00:32:30](#) until [01:26:30](#).

3.9.7 Transnational Access Info Days (4 & 11 April 2022)

On the 4th and 11th of April 2022, VITALISE organized two Info Days to help applicants that are interested to apply for Transnational Access to the Living Labs of the project discover more information about the VITALISE Living Lab research infrastructures, the [Joint Research Activities](#) and the Open Call's Application Process.

The dedicated news item is available in this [link](#).

Figure 35 Banner for the dissemination of the TA Info Days

3.9.7.1 Info Day 1

During the Info Day 1, external researchers, interested to apply for Transnational Access to the Living Lab research infrastructures of the project during the first Open Call, got familiar with the offerings of VITALISE Project and what kind of research they can conduct in each research infrastructure. More information about the Info Day 1 are available in this [link](#).

Figure 36 Poster of Info Day 1 for the 1st Open Call for Transnational Access

The full session was recorded and is available on the project's YouTube Channel in this [link](#).

3.9.7.2 Info Day 2

During Info Day 2, the interested applicants got to learn more about the Application Process for Transnational Access to the research infrastructures of VITALISE project, focusing on the main steps to be followed to successfully submit an application. More information about Info Day 2 can be found in this [link](#).

Figure 37 Poster of Info Day 2 for the 1st Open Call for Transnational Access

The full session was recorded and is available on the project's YouTube Channel in this [link](#).

3.9.8 Second Harmonisation Board and Body Meeting (27 April 2022)

The 2nd Harmonisation Board and Body Meeting of the VITALISE Project took place on the 27th of April 2022. The aim of the meeting was to discuss about the next steps regarding the harmonisation process and the Living Lab services categorization. The VITALISE [Harmonisation Board](#), a group of internal and external Living Lab and harmonisation experts that can provide expert opinions and views on the definition of the next Standard Version for Health and Wellbeing Living Labs, also joined the discussion.

Figure 38 The VITALISE Harmonisation Board

More information about the scope and purpose of the meeting are available in this [link](#), while the meeting's agenda is available on Annex 5 Second Harmonisation Board & Body Meeting Agenda". The full recorded session can be retrieved on the VITALISE YouTube Channel in this [link](#).

3.9.9 VITALISE 2nd Plenary Meeting Open Sessions (11 May 2022)

Within the framework of the Second VITALISE Plenary Meeting that took place in Helsinki, Finland, the VITALISE project partners hosted several Open Sessions. Specifically, on the 11th of May 2022, the consortium partners invited everyone interested to join virtually and learn more about the project and the latest updates regarding Living Labs and the Health & Wellbeing research community. More information about the purpose and scope of the meeting were published in [this](#) news item and the project social media accounts.

Figure 39 VITALISE Project Partners during the Second Plenary Meeting on 11 May 2022 at Laurea University

Within the framework of the meeting, the following sessions took place:

1. **The VITALISE Project overview presentation** by the Project Coordinator, Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL).
2. **Presentation of the VITALISE Harmonisation Body** by Despoina Petsani (AUTH), Teemu Santonen (LAUREA), Silia Petronikolou (AUTH) and Lina Makroglou (AUTH). The session included an exercise to map living lab services into correct categories.
3. **The VITALISE Lexicon** session by Eva Kehayia (McGill University), where McGill University, LAUREA, AUTH and ENoLL partners presented the progress of the VITALISE lexicon. The session included an interactive activity with all the partners to redefine the main categories of the Lexicon, some keywords and action points.
4. **A Promotional slot** to present the Open Calls, JRAs, Summer School, and Open Living Lab Days 2022 – Learning Lab Day 0 and Commercialisation Bootcamp.
5. A session where **representatives of other Research Infrastructure projects** funded under the same call presented their projects and the work they implement.

Figure 40 INFRAIA Projects Representatives presenting during the Second VITALISE Plenary Meeting

The featured projects and speakers were:

- [ENRIITC Project](#) - Anne Charlotte Joubert
 - [BiCIKL Project](#) - Boris Barov
 - [HITRIplus Project](#) - Angelica Facchetti
 - [EXCITE Project](#) - Sylvia Walter
6. A presentation about Research Infrastructures and “the ESFRI process” by representative of the local (Finnish) ecosystem, Marjut Kaukolehto, Science Adviser at the Academy of Finland.

Figure 41 The ESFRI Process presented by Marjut Kaukolehto

7. Showcasing the **VITALISE ICT tools** by Gorka Epelde (VICOM)
8. Showcasing the **VITALISE JRAs** by Despoina Petsani (AUTH), Vicky Van der Auwera (LICALAB) and Teemu Santonen (LAUREA).

The full session was livestreamed on the project's Facebook account and is available to watch in this [link](#).

3.9.10 Co-Creation Session “Museum Day” organized by the Medical Physics Lab of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (24 June 2022)

The Medical Physics & Digital Innovation Lab of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) organised a co-creation session on June 24, 2022 (World Museum Day) within the framework of the VITALISE Project.

Figure 42 Snapshots from the Co-creation Session organised by the Medical Physics Lab of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki during Museum Day

During this session, research associates from the lab organized an interesting Museum Day at the Museum of Casts and Antiquities in the premises of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, where participants had the chance to meet each other and exchange their experiences regarding previous museum visits, as well as share their thoughts on technology applications within this context. During the session, the invited participants, members of the AUTH Collaboration and Research Community for the Independent Living had a tour in the museum, took some photos of the exhibits that impressed them the most and then, discussed their photo choices.

3.9.11 High-Level Roundtable: Next Generation Europe (8 July 2022)

On the 8th of July 2022, three European Union-funded projects, i.e., [Schools as Living Labs](#), VITALISE and [LOOP](#), teamed up to convene the High-Level Roundtable on Next Generation Europe: How Co-Creation Can be an Answer to Europe's Biggest Challenges. The High-Level Roundtable was aimed at policy makers, as well as any interested members of the education, research and innovation ecosystems. The debate was guided by examples of current European actions in the field of Education and Health.

Figure 43 Snapshot from the High-Level Roundtable: Next Generation Europe

VITALISE Project Coordinator, Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis, and the VITALISE Scientific Coordinator, Prof. Panagiotis Bamidis joined the Round-table discussion to raise awareness about the potential of the Living Lab approach for health innovation, promoting sustainability and resilience in modern societies with citizens as active co-creators of solutions.

Figure 44 Our Project Coordinator, Evdokimos Konstantinidis, and our Scientific Coordinator, Prof. Panagiotis Bamidis at the Round-table discussion

Information about the scope and purpose of the event, as well as the full agenda can be found in this [link](#).

3.10 Training Sessions

3.10.1 First VITALISE Summer School 2022 (6 & 7 July 2022)

The first VITALISE Summer School 2022 took place on the 6th & 7th of July in Marathon (Athens area), Greece to support researchers and Living Lab beginners interested in applying the Living Lab methodology and tools in their studies and research. The event aimed to provide effective training to researchers worldwide, both on the implementation of the Living Lab methodology in their studies, as well as the involvement of Living Lab Research Infrastructures and their services in Health and Wellbeing research studies.

Figure 45 Group photo with the instructors and participants of the VITALISE Summer School 2022

Researchers and Living Lab beginners got to learn more about Open Innovation and Living Lab tools, methods and services, so as to improve their research and follow new scientific paths, with the support and instruction of the highly experienced trainers of VITALISE project.

The VITALISE Summer School was jointly organised and co-located with the School As Living Labs (SALL) / FOODSHIFT Summer School 2022. The “Schools as Sites for Food System Transformation” Summer School aims to familiarise participants with the concepts and methods of open schooling and Living Labs, providing a framework for educators and other societal actors to engage, discuss and explore how schools can become innovation incubators and accelerators within their local communities while offering new learning opportunities to their students.

The full agenda of the VITALISE Summer School 2022 is available at Annex 7 VITALISE Summer School 2022 Agenda”. More information about the scope and purpose of the Summer School are available in this [link](#).

Figure 46 Promotional Materials for the VITALISE Summer School 2022

In order to effectively promote the VITALISE Summer School 2022, several communication materials were created, including, banners, posters, leaflets, a press release and video promotions.

Figure 47 Snapshot of the video promo of Despoina Petsani's session in the VITALISE Summer School 2022

The video promos of the Summer School Sessions Instructors are available in the following links:

- Teemu Santonen (LAUREA): [Link](#)
- Despoina Petsani (AUTH): [Link](#)
- Alexandra Anagnostopoulou (AUTH): [Link](#)
- Beatriz Merino (UPM): [Link](#)
- Eva Kehayia (McGill): [Link](#)

3.11 Participation to a Conference, Workshop, Networking Event

3.11.1 2nd Open HoCare2.0 Virtual Conference (5 May 2021)

On May 5, 2021, VITALISE Project Coordinator, Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis joined the 2nd Open HoCare2.0 conference to present the VITALISE project. Organised by the National Healthcare Service Center and the Central Transdanubian Regional Innovation Agency Nonprofit Ltd. in Hungary, the 2nd Open HoCare2.0 conference showcased examples of how the co-creation process helps develop innovative products and services for home care.

Figure 48 Evdokimos Konstantinidis presenting VITALISE during the 2nd Open HoCare2.0 Conference

More information about the event and the full conference agenda can be found in this [link](#).

3.11.2 Australian Living Labs Innovations Network (31 May 2021)

On the 31st of May 2021, VITALISE Scientific Coordinator, Prof. Panagiotis Bamidis, Project Coordinator, Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis and their colleagues from the Thessaloniki Active & Healthy Ageing Living Lab - Thess-AHALL presented VITALISE Project at an online event organised by the Australian Living Labs Innovations Network.

Figure 49 Presentation of VITALISE Project during an online event organised by the Australian Living Labs Innovations Network

More information about the event are available in this [link](#).

3.11.3 Regions4PerMed online conference (13 & 14 July 2021)

On the 13th of July, Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis (Project Coordinator) presented the VITALISE Project during the Regions4PerMed Online Conference, focusing on the topic of “Harmonising Health Living Lab Infrastructures’ procedures and services”. More information about the event can be found in this [link](#).

Figure 50 Poster and Snapshot from the Regions4PerMed Online Conference

The full conference was recorded and is available in this [link](#).

3.11.4 “Let’s harmonize our Living Labs” Session during the Digital Living Lab Days 2021 (8 September 2021)

On September 8, 2021, during the Digital Living Lab Days 2021, the VITALISE project presented the “Let’s harmonize our Living Labs” session, which was inspired by the initial results of the project in the process of harmonizing Living Labs. An interactive discussion and workshop took place, aiming to create a common understanding about the services and tools each Living Lab uses (or deploys).

Figure 51 Panel of the “Let’s harmonize our Living Labs” session

Figure 52 Tuija Hirvikoski giving an overview of the Finnish social and health sector ecosystems

More information about the event can be found in this [link](#), while the full event agenda is available at Annex 8 “Let’s harmonize our Living Labs” Session - Digital Living Lab Days 2021 Agenda.

3.11.5 Interactive wall by LifeStech (UPM) (19 September 2021)

On September 19, 2021, partners from Universidad Politecnica de Madrid started a smaller scale project related to VITALISE on the interactive wall of the Smart House Living Lab. The wall is a device which allows for interaction with different users who visit the Living Lab to carry out different kinds of activities. Every year more than 3000 people visit the Smart House.

Figure 53 Interactive wall by LifeStech (UPM)

The interactive wall is currently in the design phase and the first tests will run shortly.

3.11.6 Procura's Final Event (23 September 2021)

On the 23rd of September 2021, VITALISE Project participated in the Procura Final Event with a presentation about “The Future of Living Labs in Social and Health Innovation for older adults”. Project Coordinator, Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis held a presentation about “The Future of Living Labs in Social and Health Innovation for older adults”.

More information about the event can be found in this [link](#).

3.11.7 Technology Forum at TIF Helexpo (29 September 2021)

On September 29, 2021, the VITALISE Project joined the Technology Forum event at TIF Helexpo in Thessaloniki, Greece. Project partners from the Medical Physics & Digital Innovation Lab of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki were physically present in the event, in order to speak with visitors about the project and share materials with main information about VITALISE.

Figure 54 VITALISE Project at the Technology Forum event at TIF Helexpo

More information about the event can be found in this [link](#).

3.11.8 Epicur AUTH flagship event (24-26 November 2021)

On the 2nd Annual Epicur AUTH flagship event, hosted virtually by the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki on 24-26 November 2021, VITALISE Scientific Coordinator, Prof. Panagiotis Bamidis, participated in a panel discussion for advancing student mobility with emphasis on the role of Living Labs, presenting also the work implemented in this direction within the VITALISE Project.

Figure 55 Panagiotis Bamidis in a panel discussion during the Epicur AUTH flagship event

More information about the event can be found in this [link](#).

3.11.9 2nd KLID-FNF Living Lab Forum “Citizen-Driven Innovation for More Sustainable Cities” (7 December 2021)

On the 7th of December 2021, partners from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki attended the 2nd KLID-FNF Living Lab Forum for “Citizen-Driven Innovation for More Sustainable Cities” online, presenting the Thess-AHALL and VITALISE as part of the Living Lab performed activities.

During session 1, VITALISE Project Coordinator, Evdokimos Konstantinidis, held a presentation under the topic “Introduction of Living Labs from European perspective”, while project’s Scientific Coordinator, Panos Bamidis and Research Associate Despoina Petsani presented about “Fostering Citizen Engagement: ThessAhall Living Lab for Health”.

Figure 56 Snapshots from the 2nd KLID-FNF Living Lab Forum “Citizen-Driven Innovation for More Sustainable Cities”

The event was recorded and is available in this [link](#), while the full event agenda is available at Annex 10 2nd KLID-FNF Living Lab Forum “Citizen-Driven Innovation for More Sustainable Cities” Agenda.

3.11.10 “Experiences of innovation in the aging sector” event of Living Lab Bidealde in Pamplona, Spain (3 March 2022)

Figure 57 Poster of the "Experiencias de innovación en envejecimiento" event

VITALISE Project partner, Fundación Intrás, presented the VITALISE Project in the "Experiences of innovation in the aging sector" (Experiencias de innovación en envejecimiento) event, on March 3, 2022, organized by Bidealde Living Lab in Pamplona, Spain. More information about this event are available in this [link](#).

3.11.11 Europe2022FR High-level Conference (22 March 2022)

VITALISE Project Coordinator and President of the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis, presented the VITALISE Project to the Europe2022FR High-level Conference in Paris, on the 22nd of March 2022. The scope of the meeting was to exchange on the evolution of Living Labs in Health and Autonomy in France and Europe and to explore future collaborations between ENoLL and Forum LLSA.

More information regarding the event can be found in this [link](#).

3.11.12 Quebec Society for Research in Psychology Conference (Congrès de la Société québécoise pour la recherche en psychologie) (SQRP) (21 May 2022)

On May 21st 2022 partners from the McGill - Udem- CRIR Living Lab of VITALISE Project, i.e., Trépanier, L, Nadeau, S, Fortier-Hébert, J, Higgins, J., Kehayia, E., Poldma, T., Saj, A. and de Guise, E., participated in the Quebec Society for Research in Psychology Conference (SQRP) 2022 (original: “Congrès de la Société québécoise pour la recherche en psychologie (SQRP) 2022”) at

Manoir St Sauveur in Quebec, Canada. Our partners presented a preliminary study about the impacts of a museum visit on pain, fatigue, stress and well-being following a stroke, including some of their work implemented within VITALISE Project.

More information about the event can be found in this [link](#), while the full conference agenda is available in this [link](#).

3.11.13 Virtual Learning Lab by ENoLL | Session 8: Evaluation & Impacts of Living Labs (31 May 2022)

The Virtual Learning Lab brings together a community of participants and experts in exchanging knowledge on the key elements of Living Labs. VITALISEProject Coordinator hosted a session on the 31st of May 2022, on the “Evaluation and Impacts of Living Labs”, inspired by the work implemented within the VITALISE Project.

Figure 58 Snapshots from the video promo of Evdokimos Konstantinidis for his session during the Virtual Learning Lab

More information about the Virtual Learning Lab can be found in this [link](#).

3.11.14 4th Quebec Congress of Research in Adaptation-Rehabilitation (4e Congrès québécois de recherche en adaptation-réadaptation) (4 June 2022)

On June 4, 2022, the VITALISE partners from McGill – UDEM – CRIR Living Lab, i.e., Trépanier, L., Nadeau, S., Fortier-Hébert, J., Higgins, J., Kehayia, E., Poldma, T., Saj, A. and de Guise, E., joined the 4th Quebec Congress of Research in Adaptation-Rehabilitation (original: “4e Congrès québécois de recherche en adaptation-réadaptation”) event that took place at Hotel Delta Sherbrooke in Quebec, Canada to present a preliminary study about the impacts of a museum visit on pain, fatigue, stress and well-being following a stroke, including some of their work implemented within VITALISE Project.

More information about the event can be found in this [link](#), while the abstract of the preliminary study can be found on page 59 of the file in this [link](#).

3.11.15 ISPIM Innovation Conference 2022 (6 & 7 June 2022)

The 2022 ISPIM Innovation Conference – “Innovating in a Digital World” – took place in Copenhagen, Denmark from 5-8 June 2022.

On Monday, 6 June 2022, VITALISEProject Coordinator, Evdokimos Konstantinidis joined the conference with a presentation under the topic “Towards a Taxonomy for Health Living Lab Data Collection Devices”, sharing the knowledge that is being developed in this direction within the framework of VITALISE Project. More information about his presentation are available in this [link](#).

Figure 59 Evdokimos Konstantinidis presenting during the ISPIM Innovation Conference 2022

Then, on the 7th of June 2022, VITALISE partner, Koen Vervoort from the European Network of Living Labs also joined the ISPIM INNOVATION CONFERENCE 2022 with a presentation under the topic “Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs: a standardized evaluation framework”.

Figure 60 Koen Vervoort from the European Network of Living Labs presenting during the ISPIM INNOVATION CONFERENCE 2022

More information about Koen’s presentation can be accessed through this [link](#).

3.11.16 Bilbao Basque Ocean Week (9 June 2022)

On June 9, 2022, Idoia Muñoz, on behalf of Cluster GAIA, had the opportunity to present during the “BILBAO BASQUE OCEAN WEEK” the Ozean Living Lab as an ecosystem for the well-being of the citizens, and more specifically the activities that are being organized within VITALISE Project. Idoia explained how sustainable territories, and in Ozean Living Lab’s case the Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve, can contribute to improving people’s well-being by incorporating within the definition of “sustainability” not only environmental, economic and social criteria, but also well-being of the population. In this new incorporation, the environment, art and culture also play an essential role (the fifth helix).

Figure 61 Idoia Munoz presenting VITALISE during Bilbao Basque Ocean Week

More information about the event can be found in this [link](#).

3.11.17 AGE-WELL EPIC Conference (9 June 2022)

On June 9, 2022, Nancy Azevedo from McGill UdeM CRIR Living Lab joined the AGE-WELL EPIC Conference, with a presentation regarding “Le développement de technologies avec et pour les

personnes âgées: l'effet catalyseur des laboratoires vivants”. The agenda of the event is available in this [link](#).

The full presentation was uploaded on YouTube and it can be accessed through this [link](#).

3.11.18 8th International Conference on Time Series and Forecasting, Gran Canaria, Spain (ITISE 2022) (29 June 2022)

On 29 June, our partners from VICOMTECH joined the 8th International Conference on Time Series and Forecasting, Gran Canaria, Spain (ITISE 2022) with a presentation regarding “Synthetic Subject Generation with Coupled Coherent Time Series Data”.

Figure 62 Mikel Hernandez (VICOMTECH) presenting during the 8th International Conference on Time Series and Forecasting

More information about the event can be found in this [link](#), while the research paper that was presented in available in this [link](#).

3.11.19 Next Door Project Conference focused on "Activate Community to fight Isolation and Loneliness of the Older Citizens" (1 July 2022)

On July 1st, 2022, our partners from Fundacion Intrax held a presentation at the Next Door Project Conference under the topic “Experience of using Living Labs for active and healthy aging”. VITALISE was presented as one of the projects that strengthen the Living Lab community and performance.

The full event agenda is available at Annex 9 Next Door Project Conference Agenda”.

3.12 Meetings with the Research Infrastructure Community (Synergies)

Apart from the active presence and participation of the VITALISE partners in conferences and other networking events, in the initial phase of the project, the VITALISE Project Coordinator, Dr Evdokimos Konstantinidis, the Scientific Coordinator of the project, Prof. Panos Bamidis, Despoina Petsani (Harmonisation Board Coordinator) and Ada Pellumbaj (Dissemination and Communication Manager) met with several project managers of INFRAIA EU-funded projects to discuss about the optimisation of the Transnational Access provision processes, as well as deciding on the optimal selection criteria for the applicants of the Open Calls. What is more, both sides expressed interest for the exploration of collaboration opportunities and the promotion of common interests and goals.

Figure 63 Snapshots from meetings of the VITALISE partners with the Research Infrastructures Community

Indicatively, VITALISE contacted several projects, such as:

- MINKE project: [Link](#)
- MOSBRI project: [Link](#)
- Co-Udlabs project: [Link](#)
- BiCIKL project: [Link](#)
- EXCITE Network: [Link](#)
- PRISMAP project: [Link](#)
- HITRIplus Project: [Link](#)
- ENRIITC Project: [Link](#)

The discussions were very fruitful with interesting outcomes and essential exchange of knowledge. As a result, the VITALISE partners proposed to maintain contacts with the other INFRAIA projects and created the research-infrastructures@googlegroups.com mailing list and Google group, where all INFRAIA projects are encouraged to reach out to the community regarding questions, joint event organization, etc. Currently, **more than 40 members** from the Research Infrastructures community have joined this group.

One of the first outcomes of this networking initiative was the “Long-term sustainability of small & mid-scale distributed Research Infrastructure projects” ICRI 2022 side event that VITALISE co-organised with MOSBRI project, ESF and Europlanet within the framework of the ICRI 2022 Conference.

Figure 64 Banner of the “Long-term sustainability of small & mid-scale distributed Research Infrastructure projects” ICRI 2022 side event

The event will take place on Wednesday, 19 October 2022 from 9:00-12:00am in a hybrid form, with in-person attendance capacity and unlimited online participation spots. More information can be found in this [link](#).

4 Performance and Outreach of the VITALISE Dissemination and Communication Activities

This section provides an overview of the performance and outreach achieved through the channels of the VITALISE Project. For the purposes of this documents, outreach (reach) is defined as the number of times a message related to the VITALISE project has reached people from the identified target audiences.

4.1 Outreach through partners' social media

Table 5 lists the social media posts that the VITALISE partners have posted on their channels until M18, along with their estimated outreach.

Table 5 List of Partners' social media posts and outreach

List of Partners' social media posts and outreach							
Date	Partner	Title of activity	URL	Research Community	Policy Makers	Society	Media
24/3/21	INTRAS	Information on the start of the vitalise project	Link	-	-	-	-
5/4/21	AV	GENERAL PROJECT PROMOTION	Link	-	-	103	-
14/4/21	TREBAG	On the start of Vitalise and LLs on Trebag FB page	Link	-	-	-	-
14/4/21	TREBAG	On the start of Vitalise and LLs on Trebag FB page	Link	20	-	500	-
19/4/21	AV	GENERAL PROJECT PROMOTION	Link	-	-	68	-
19/4/21	SIT	info about the kick-off meeting	Link	-	-	400	-
19/4/21	SIT	info about the kick-off meeting	Link	-	-	400	-
19/4/21	SIT	Info about the Kick-off meeting	Link	-	-	50	-
20/4/21	INTRAS	info about the kick-off meeting	Link	-	-	-	-
20/4/21	SIT	Info about open sessions	Link	-	-	-	-
20/4/21	TREBAG	On the brainstorming in Vitalise kick off on open innovation and LLs	Link	-	-	500	-
21/4/21	SIT	Final day of the kick-off meeting	Link	-	-	1000	-
21/4/21	SIT	Info about the final day of the kick-off meeting	Link	-	-	400	-
21/4/21	SIT	Info about final day of the kick-off meeting	Link	-	-	200	-

D13.2 Dissemination and Communication activities report (first version)

28/6/21	AV	PROMOTION OF NEWSLETTER	Link	-	-	55	-
21/9/21	TREBAG	Sharing Vitalise webpage on Trebag FB	Link	-	-		-
21/9/21	TREBAG	Sharing Vitalise webpage on Trebag FB	Link	40	20	500	-
22/9/21	TREBAG	Post on Trebag's FB page on Vitalise	Link	50	40	500	-
23/9/21	TREBAG	Post on Vitalise FB page in Hungarian by Trebag	Link	100		300	-
24/9/21	SIT	Info about the project	Link	-	-	150	-
24/9/21	SIT	info about the project	Link	-	-	50	-
27/9/21	AV	GENERAL PROJECT PROMOTION	Link	-	-	34	-
29/9/21	AV	GENERAL PROJECT PROMOTION	Link	-	-	172	-
29/9/21	INTRAS	Learning from others. Looking to the future. The VITALISE Project presented by the ENoLL chairperson	Link	+10	+10	+20	-
30/9/21	INTRAS	VITALISE Newsletter subscription	Link	-	-	-	-
29/11/21	SIT	Info about the open sessions	Link	-	-	-	-
29/11/21	SIT	Info about the open sessions	Link	-	-	150	-
30/11/21	INTRAS	VITALISE Plenary Meeting	Link	-	-	-	-
30/11/21	SIT	Info about the open sessions	Link	-	-	100	-
31/1/22	LICALAB	Vitalise: use cases over transitie van acute zorg	Link	-	-	-	-
31/1/22	LICALAB	Newsletter item + website item: H2020-project Vitalise publiceert twee use cases	Link	-	-	-	-
5/2/22	AV	GENERAL PROJECT PROMOTION	Link	-	-	6	-
9/2/22	INTRAS	VITALISE Project	Link	-	-	-	-
14/2/22	SIt	Info Call External Evaluator	Link	-	-	100	-
14/2/22	SIT	Info Call External Evaluator	Link	-	-	150	-

D13.2 Dissemination and Communication activities report (first version)

9/3/22	SIT	VITALISE call for External Evaluators - EXTENDED	Link	-	-	180	-
9/3/22	SIT	VITALISE call for External Evaluators - EXTENDED	Link	-	-	150	-
10/3/22	SIT	1st Open Call	Link	-	-	70	-
10/3/22	TUE	LinkedIn post	Link	4	5	-	10
30/3/22	SIT	1st info Day for the Open Call	Link	-	-	110	-
30/3/22	SIT	1st info Day for the Open Call	Link	-	-	90	-
30/3/22	SIT	1st info Day for the Open Call	Link	-	-		-
7/4/22	SIT	Post	Link	-	-	100	-
7/4/22	SIT	Post	Link	-	-	115	-
29/4/22	TUE	Share about the Open Call for Transnational Access	Link	5	10	230	6
6/5/22	INTRAS	Last days of the VITALISE OpenCall1 for researchers	Link	-	-	-	-
6/5/22	INTRAS	Informing about the second workshop on the design of a self-assessment tool that will help LivingLabs to improve their processes, methodologies and practice of innovation centered on the user and real life contexts	Link	-	-	-	-
9/5/22	INTRAS	Informing about the open sessions at the second plenary meeting (promotion)	Link	-	-	-	-
10/5/22	SIT	Open Session Plenary meeting	Link	-	-	50	-
16/6/22	SIT	Info about the bootcamp	Link	-	-	110	-
16/6/22	SIT	Info about the bootcamp	Link	-	-	80	-
1/7/22	INTRAS	Experience of using Living Lab for active and healthy aging.		-	-	-	-
8/7/22	INTRAS	Informing about the Summer School experience	Link	-	-	-	-
Total reach				229	85	10924	16

4.2 Dissemination and outreach from the various publications associated with VITALISE

Table 6 sums up the outreach that VITALISE Project achieved through the various publications stemming from the project or related to the project.

Table 6 Outreach from publications online

Outreach from publications online							
Date	Partner	Title	Medium	Research community	Policy makers	Society	Media
31/1/21	LICALAB	Vitalise: use cases about transitional care (original: <i>Vitalise: use cases over transitie van acute zorg</i>)	Newsletter	-	-	1500	-
31/3/21	INTRAS	VITALISE, the European project at the service of Living Lab harmonization that shows us the importance of empathy (original: VITALISE, el proyecto europeo al servicio de la armonización Living Lab que nos marca la importancia de la empatía)	Fundación Intras website	-	-	100	-
14/4/21	TREBAG	VITALISE	Trebag website	90	20	500	40
19/4/21	AUTH	Transfer of know-how and access to new researchers to the Living Lab research infrastructures of AUTH (original: Μεταφορά τεχνογνωσίας και πρόσβαση νέων ερευνητών στις ερευνητικές υποδομές των "Ζωντανών Εργαστηρίων" του ΑΠΘ)	Αθηναϊκό - Μακεδονικό Πρακτορείο Ειδήσεων	-	-	>5000	1
26/4/21	SIT	VITALISE: the launch of the new H2020 project	SocialIT website	-	-	80	-
27/4/21	N/A	VITALISE Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure	RRI Tools website	-	-	500	-
29/4/21	LICALAB	VITALISE: harmonization of procedures for living labs in the field of health and well-being (original: VITALISE: harmonisatie	LiCalab website	-	-	1500	-

D13.2 Dissemination and Communication activities report (first version)

		van procedures voor proeftuinen in het domein van gezondheid en welzijn)					
30/4/21	UPM	Virtual health And wellbeing Living Lab InfraStructurE	LifeSTech website	-	-	200	-
30/4/21	INTRAS	Starts H2020 VITALISE project of harmonization and virtual infrastructure of Living Labs of health and well-being	Fundacion Intras website	-	-	100	-
1/5/21	AV	VITALISE	Anthology Ventures website	-	-	120	-
31/5/21	LICALAB	Vitalise-horizon-2020	LiCalab website	-	-	1500	-
1/6/21	VILABS	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure H2020 VITALISE project kicked off	CORDIS EU	-	-	3000	-
1/6/21	SIT	Information about the Vitalise project	SocialIT website	-	-	50	-
17/6/21	TREBAG	Participation in two Horizon 2020 project consortia (original: Két Horizon 2020 projekt konzorciumban vevszünk részt)	TREBAG	-	-	80	-
28/6/21	LICALAB	Vitalise: 19 European living labs are building living lab standards and procedures (original: Vitalise: 19 Europese living labs bouwen aan living lab standaarden en procedures)	Newsletter	-	-	1500	-
30/6/21	VILABS	VITALISE	VR4REH AB online library	-	-	500	-
22/9/21	ENoLL	Receive the latest news from VITALISE project	ENoLL website	-	-	4000	-
29/9/21	ENoLL	Everyone is welcome to join the VITALISE Harmonization Body for Living Labs	ENoLL website	-	-	4000	-

D13.2 Dissemination and Communication activities report (first version)

20/12/21	LICALAB	Vitalise: help us improve our wiki page (original: <i>Vitalise: help onze wiki-pagina te verbeteren</i>)	Newsletter	-	-	1500	-
6/1/22	N/A	Cocreating a Harmonized Living Lab for Big Data–Driven Hybrid Persona Development: Protocol for Cocreating, Testing, and Seeking Consensus	JMIR Research Protocols	982	-	-	-
19/1/22	N/A	Digital Biomarkers for Supporting Transitional Care Decisions: Protocol for a Transnational Feasibility Study	JMIR Research Protocols	581	-	-	-
31/1/22	LICALAB	H2020-project Vitalise publiceert twee use cases	LiCalab website	-	-	1500	-
1/2/22	AUTH	Our News – Issue 10 (Τα Νέα μας - Τεύχος 10)	Newsletter	-	-	1500	-
9/2/22	INTRAS	VITALISE	Fundacion Intras website	-	-	120	-
1/3/22	VILABS	Transnational Access to the RIs of VITALISE Project - Info Days	CORDIS EU	-	-	3000	-
1/3/22	VILABS	Apply for free access to the Research Infrastructures of the European VITALISE Project (original: <i>Κάντε Αίτηση για Δωρεάν Πρόσβαση στις Ερευνητικές Υποδομές του Ευρωπαϊκού Έργου VITALISE</i>)	Eduguide	-	-	50000	-
1/3/22	AUTH	Our News – Issue 11 (Τα Νέα μας - Τεύχος 11)	Newsletter	-	-	1500	-
9/3/22	N/A	Incorporation of Synthetic Data Generation Techniques within a Controlled Data Processing Workflow in the Health and Wellbeing Domain	MDPI	5646	-	-	-
10/3/22	N/A	Rehabilitation Supported by Technology: Protocol for an International	JMIR Research	593	-	-	-

		Cocreation and User Experience Study	h Protocols				
10/3/22	TUE	The kick-off of VITALISE Project (Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure) (original: <i>Start VITALISE met Virtuele Gezondheid en Welzijn Living Lab Infrastructuur</i>)	Slimmer Leven	53	4	2	5
31/3/22	LICALAB	[Vitalise] Rehabilitation Supported by Technology: Protocol for an International Co-Creation and User Experience Study (original: <i>[Vitalise] Revalidatie Ondersteund door Technologie: Protocol voor een internationaal 'co-creatie en gebruikerservaring'-onderzoek</i>)	LiCalab website	-	-	1500	-
31/3/22	LICALAB	Vitalise makes its infrastructure available for transnational access (original: <i>Vitalise stelt infrastructuur ter beschikking voor transnationaal onderzoek</i>)	Newsletter	-	-	1500	-
28/4/22	LICALAB	Vitalise organizes a Summer School in Greece (original: <i>Vitalise organiseert Summer School in Griekenland</i>)	Newsletter	-	-	1500	-
31/5/22	LICALAB	Vitalise: partners meet in Finland (original: <i>Vitalise: partners ontmoeten elkaar in Finland</i>)	LiCalab website	-	-	1500	-
5/6/22	N/A	Towards a taxonomy for health living lab data collection devices	XXXIII ISPIM Innovation Conference Proceedings	450	-	-	-
5/6/22	N/A	Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs:	XXXIII ISPIM Innovation	450	-	-	-

		a standardized evaluation framework	n Conference Proceedings				
14/6/22	AUTH	Our News – Issue 14 (Τα Νέα μας - Τεύχος 14)	Newsletter	-	-	1500	-
21/6/22	N/A	Synthetic Subject Generation with Coupled Coherent Time Series Data	MDPI	264	-	-	-
Total				9109	24	90852	46

4.3 Dissemination and outreach through the organisation of events

This section provides an overview of the outreach achieved through the organisation of events within the framework of the VITALISE Project.

Table 7 Outreach through the organisation of events

Outreach from Organisation of Events					
Date	Title	Research community	Policymakers	Society	Media
20/4/21	Kick-off meeting open sessions	50	-	135	-
1/6/21	“Establishment of Evaluation Processes and Tools” Workshop	25	-	-	-
1/7/21	“Harmonisation of Living Lab Services Terminology” Workshop	35	-	43	-
2/7/21	“VITALISE Technology Demonstrations” Open Session	48	-	109	-
30/11/21	VITALISE Plenary Meeting Open Sessions	62	-	99	-
4/4/22	Transnational Access Info Day 1	95	-	80	-
11/4/22	Transnational Access Info Day 2	48	-	86	-
27/4/22	Second Harmonisation Board and Body Meeting	30	-	21	-
11/5/22	VITALISE 2nd Plenary Meeting Opens Sessions	80	-	-	-
24/6/22	Co-Creation Session “Museum Day”	10	-	21	-
6/7/22	First VITALISE Summer School 2022	30	-	19	-

8/7/22	High-Level Roundtable: Next Generation Europe	30	20	50	5
Total reach		543	20	663	5

4.4 Dissemination and outreach through participation to events

This section, and specifically Table 8 Stakeholder outreach through participation to events, etc., elaborates on the outreach achieved through the presentation of VITALISE and the participation of the project partners to external events.

Table 8 Stakeholder outreach through participation to events, etc.

Outreach from participation to events					
Date	Title	Research community	Policymakers	Society	Media
5/5/21	2nd Open HoCare2.0 Virtual Conference	64	-	-	-
31/5/21	Australian Living Labs Innovations Network	12	-	-	-
13/7/21	Regions4PerMed online conference	10	-	446	-
8/9/21	“Let’s harmonise our Living Labs” Session during the Digital Living Lab Days 2021	65	-	-	-
19/9/21	Interactive wall by LifeStech (UPM)	-	-	>3000	-
23/9/21	Procura's Final Event	50	-	-	-
29/9/21	Technology Forum at TIF Helexpo	-	-	>1000	-
24/11/21	Epicur AUTH flagship event	37	-	-	-
7/12/21	2nd KLID-FNF Living Lab Forum “Citizen-Driven Innovation for More Sustainable Cities”	100	-	13	-
3/3/21	Experiences of innovation in the aging sector (Experiencias de innovación en envejecimiento) event of Living Lab Bidealde in Pamplona, Spain	50	-	-	-
22/3/22	Europe2022FR High-level Conference	100	-	-	-
21/5/22	Quebec Society for Research in Psychology Conference 2022 (original: “Congrès de la Société québécoise pour la recherche en psychologie (SQRP)”)	450	-	-	-

31/5/22	Virtual Learning Lab by ENOLL Session 8: Evaluation & Impacts of Living Labs	-	-	50	-
4/6/22	4th Quebec Congress of Research in Adaptation-Rehabilitation (original: <i>4e Congrès québécois de recherche en adaptation-réadaptation</i>)	115	15	-	-
6/6/22	ISPIM Innovation Conference 2022	450	-	-	-
9/6/22	Bilbao Basque Ocean Week	30	100	500000	2
9/6/22	AGE-WELL EPIC Conference	20	-	-	-
29/6/22	8th International Conference on Time Series and Forecasting, Gran Canaria, Spain (ITISE 2022)	150	-	-	-
1/7/22	Next Door Project Conference focused on "Activate Community to fight Isolation and Loneliness of the Older Citizens"	100	-	-	-
Total reach		1803	115	504509	2

4.5 Summary of the outreach achieved through all dissemination activities

This section summarises the reach attained through all the dissemination and communication activities and channels of the VITALISE Project from M1 until M18.

Table 9 Summary table of the total reach of the VITALISE Dissemination and Communication Activities

Outreach from the VITALISE Dissemination and Communication Activities					
No.	Type of Activity/Medium	Research community	Policymakers	Society	Media
1	Website	-	-	7200	-
2	VITALISE social media	-	-	132000	-
3	Partners' social media	229	85	10924	16
4	Various publications (Media, Newsletters, Scientific Publications, etc.)	9109	24	90852	46
5	Organisation of events	543	20	663	5
6	Participation to events	1803	115	504509	2
7	Synergies	40	-	-	-
Total		11724	224	987687	69

Appendices

Appendix 1 Kick-Off Meeting Agenda

Programme (Tuesday 20 April, CEST)

- 12.30 - 12.45**
Welcome
Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL - AUTH), Fernando Villarino (ENoLL), Tuija Hirvikoski (LAUREA), Panagiotis Bamidis (AUTH), Efstratios Stylianidis (Vice Rector for Research AUTH), Kyriakos Anastasiadis (Head of the School of Medicine AUTH)
- 12.45 - 13.00**
EU vision for Research
Johannes Klumpers, Senior Expert, Climate Adaptation, European Commission
- 13.00 - 13.10**
Project Presentation
Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL - AUTH)
- 13.10 - 13.25**
VITALISE Joint Research Activities
Despoina Petsani (AUTH), Vicky Van der Auwera (LICALAB), Teemu Santonen (LAUREA)
- 13.25 - 13.35**
VITALISE Open Calls - WP11
Valentina Conotter (SIT)
- 13.35 - 13.45**
Coffee Break
- 13.45 - 14.30**
Living Lab Infrastructure presentation
Partners representatives
- 14.30 - 15.15**
Harmonization of Health and Wellbeing Living Labs - WP2
Despoina Petsani (AUTH), Teemu Santonen (LAUREA)
- 15.15 - 15.30**
Coffee Break
- 15.30 - 16.30**
Round table discussion on "Healthy, happy and socially inclusive cities"
Moderator: Ugo Guarnacci, Project Adviser, EREA, European Commission
Panelists:
 - Maria Yeroyanni, Senior Expert innovating Cities, DG R&I, European Commission
 - Maria Vasile, Scientific Project Adviser, HADEA, European Commission
 - Prof Leonidas Pavlidis, School of Medicine, University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)
 - Prof Denia Kolokotsa, Technical University of Crete Kounoupidiana, Coordinator of H2020 Varcities
 - Prof Marina Della Giusta, University of Reading, H2020 project IN-HABIT**Conclusions by Ugo Guarnacci**
- 16.30 - 16.40**
Coffee Break
- 16.40 - 17.20**
Capacity Building and educational material - WP4
Ines Vaittinen (ENoLL)

Contact details

- <https://vitalise-project.eu>
- <https://twitter.com/VITALISEproject>
- <https://www.facebook.com/VITALISEproject/>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/vitalise-project/>
- Project coordinator: Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis (info@vitalise-project.eu)

Annex 2 “Establishment of Evaluation Processes & Tools” Workshop Agenda

VITALISE Co-Creative Discussion: **Establishment of Evaluation Processes & Tools**

1 June 2021, 13.00 - 15.00h CEST
via Zoom

Hands-On Workshop Agenda

A background network diagram consisting of various colored nodes (blue, green, red, purple, cyan) connected by thin grey lines, forming a complex web-like structure.

13.00-13.05	Welcome (Forum LLSA)
13.05-13.15	Set the scene (ENoLL)
13.15-13.30	Missing areas & voting most important areas
13.30-13.35	Break
13.35-14.20	Scope the criteria and make them smart (break out rooms)
14.20-14.50	Consolidation & reporting to the plenary session
14.50-15.00	Next steps & wrap-up (Thes-AHALL)

Annex 3 “Harmonisation of Living Lab Services Terminology” Workshop

Harmonization of Living Lab provided services terminology

1 July 2021, 15:00-17:00 CEST
via Microsoft Teams

Workshop Agenda

A background network diagram consisting of various colored nodes (blue, green, red, purple) connected by thin grey lines, creating a complex web-like structure.

15:00-15:10	Introduction & Welcome
15:10-15:25	Presentation of researchers use cases
15:25-15:35	Presentation of data collection classification
15:35-16:25	Services and procedures offered by Living Labs
16:25-16:40	Research process phases
16:40-16:50	Innovation process phases
16:50-17:00	Business model of Living Labs

Annex 4 Plenary Meeting Open Sessions Agenda (30 November 2021)

VITALISE
Virtual Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure

VITALISE Plenary Meeting Agenda
Tuesday, 30 November 2021
13.30 - 17.00 CEST

13.30 - 13.50
Overview of the Joint Research Activities (JRAs)
Despoina Petsani
Vicky Van der Auwera
Teemu Santonen

13.50 - 14.00
Pilot Monitoring
Beatriz Merino
Gloria Cea Sánchez

14.00 - 15.00
1st Harmonisation Body Meeting Open Discussion
Despoina Petsani

15.10 - 16.10
Workshop on Living Lab labeling and KPIs
Koen Vervoort
David Servais

16.10 - 17.00
Workshop on ICT tools requirements
Despoina Mantziari
Alexandra Anagnostopoulou
Despoina Petsani

Scan to join the meeting

Scan Here

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socialIT software & consulting
LAU REA
LiCalab
intras
TREBAG
GAIA
vicintech
CERTH
AIT
socialIT
wilda
iLabs
FORUM LLSA
TU/e
McGill
Université de Montréal
CPA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101007900.

Annex 5 Second Harmonisation Board & Body Meeting Agenda

SECOND HARMONISATION BODY MEETING

Details Day: Wednesday, 27 April 2022
 Time: 14.00 - 16.00 CET
 Place: Online via Zoom

Scan to register

Agenda

Time	Agenda Item	Presenter
5'	Welcome & introduction	Evdokimos Konstantinidis & Despoina Petsani
5'	General update about the harmonisation process & the current standard version.	Despoina Petsani
10'	Presentation of the services & possible categorisation	Silia Petronikolou
30'	Ideation on how to do the services categorisation through miro	Teemu Santonen & all presenters
30'	Break-out rooms for discussion in small groups about the categories through miro	All presenters
5'-10'	Closing & next steps	Despoina Petsani

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Annex 6 Second Plenary Meeting Open Session Agenda

Virtual Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure
VITALISE Plenary Meeting
Wednesday, 11 May 2022
9.45 - 17.00 CEST
Online via Zoom

JOIN US!

VITALISE harmonises Health & Wellbeing Living Lab procedures and opens up Living Lab infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote open Research & Innovation in Europe and beyond.

9.45-10.00 VITALISE project overview Evdokimos Konstantinidis	10.00-10.45 VITALISE Harmonisation Despoina Petsani Teemu Santonen Silia Petronikolou	10.45-11.00 VITALISE Lexicon Eva Kehayia	11.00-11.15 Promotional slot (Open calls, summer school, Francesca Spagnoli)
11.30-11.45 Health Capital Helsinki Juha Paakkola	11.45-12.00 Living Labs as Research Infrastructures – the ESFRI Roadmap	12.00-12.15 Initiative for RIs in EU Anne-Charlotte Joubert-ENRIITC Boris Barov- BICIKL	12.15-13.15 Living labs in existing initiatives Sharing best practices – Envisioning the Future
14.15-15.00 Showcasing the VITALISE ICT tools Gorka Epelde	15.00-15.45 Showcasing the VITALISE JRAs	16.00-17.00 Forum – Demonstration of technologies Poster & demonstration session	Join us virtually! SCAN FOR INFO

Project coordinator: Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis
Scientific coordinator: Prof. Panos Bamidis,

<https://vitalise-project.eu> [@VITALISEproject](https://twitter.com/VITALISEproject) [VITALISE H2020 project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/vitalise-h2020-project)
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Annex 7 VITALISE Summer School 2022 Agenda

VITALISE Summer School 2022

Supporting researchers and Living Lab beginners to apply the Living Lab methodology and tools in their research studies.

1

General Information

- **Date:** 6 and 7 July 2022
- **Location:** Marathon (Athens Region, Greece)
- **Venue:** Golden Coast Hotel
- **Target audience:** Researchers and living lab beginners interested in applying the Living Lab methodology and tools in their studies and research.
- **Available spots:** 30
- **Registration deadline:** 6 June

2

About the Summer School

The VITALISE Summer School aims to provide effective training to researchers worldwide, both on the implementation of the Living Lab methodology in their studies, as well as the involvement of Living Lab Research Infrastructures and their services in Health and Wellbeing research studies.

The participants get access to the VITALISE ICT tools and e-infrastructure to collaborate on scientific research with other Living Labs recognized and labelled by the European Network of Living Labs.

3

What to expect

The VITALISE Summer School includes:

- 5 hours of expert lectures
- 5 hours of hands-on workshops to improve your research
- 1-hour inspirational interaction with representatives of projects using the Living Lab methodology
- All materials and equipment needed for the course
- Catering (complementary lunch and coffee breaks)
- A Social Programme & organisation of excursions

4

Let's connect

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info@vitalise-project.eu

Project Coordinator: Evdokimos Konstantinidis

Scientific Coordinator: Panagiotis Bamidis

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VITALISE Summer School 2022

Supporting researchers and Living Lab beginners to apply the Living Lab methodology and tools in their research studies.

Agenda for Day 1 (6 July 2022)

Living Labs methods & tools for researchers

<p>09:00 - 10:00</p>	<p>Evdokimos Konstantinidis Francesca Spagnoli</p> <p>ENoLL - European Network of Living Labs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome and objectives Living Labs basics, benefits and challenges 	<p>1</p>
<p>10:00 - 11:00</p>	<p>Despoina Petsani</p> <p>AUTH - Aristotle University of Thessaloniki</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How researchers can be involved and use Living Labs in their daily job: case studies 	<p>2</p>
<p>11:00 - 12:00</p>	<p>Session moderated by Leidy Enriquez</p> <p>ENoLL - European Network of Living Labs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tour de table: get to know each other 	<p>3</p>
<p>12:00 - 13:00</p>	<p>Teemu Santonen</p> <p>LAUREA University of Applied Sciences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Living Lab innovation processes and services 	<p>4</p>
<p>13:00 - 14:00</p>	<p>Lunch Break</p>	<p>5</p>
<p>14:00 - 16:00</p>	<p>Session moderated by Teemu Santonen</p> <p>LAUREA University of Applied Sciences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hands on exercise on selected methods & services for small research design and peer to peer learning 	<p>6</p>
<p>16:00</p>	<p>Excursion to the Acropolis Museum and dinner (optional)</p>	<p>7</p>

Agenda for Day 2 (7 July 2022)

Co-creating with Living Labs to improve your research

<p>10:00 - 11:00</p>	<p>Alexandra Anagnostopoulou</p> <p>AUTH - Aristotle University of Thessaloniki</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data ownership within Living Labs 	<p>1</p>
<p>11:00 - 12:00</p>	<p>Beatriz Merino</p> <p>UPM - Universidad Politecnica de Madrid</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experimentation & co-creation in a real-life environment 	<p>2</p>
<p>12:00 - 13:00</p>	<p>Session moderated by Beatriz Merino</p> <p>UPM - Universidad Politecnica de Madrid</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hands on exercise: co-creation session on your selected research cases 	<p>3</p>
<p>13:00 - 14:00</p>	<p>Lunch Break</p>	<p>4</p>
<p>14:00 - 15:30</p>	<p>Eva Kehayia</p> <p>McGill University</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How to change my research through Living Labs 	<p>5</p>
<p>15:30 - 16:30</p>	<p>Inspirational session with representatives from LifeChamps and other research projects where Living Labs were included.</p>	<p>6</p>
<p>16:30 - 17:30</p>	<p>Joint SALL & VITALISE Summer School Workshop</p>	<p>7</p>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

Annex 8 “Let’s harmonise our Living Labs” Session - Digital Living Lab Days 2021 Agenda

#DLLD21 session:

Let’s harmonize our Living Labs!

8 September 2021

Agenda

Welcome and objectives

- Despoina Petsani, Research Associate, Lab of Medical Physics, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
- Evdokimos Konstantinidis, Postdoctoral Research Associate, Lab of Medical Physics, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

Setting the scene – Panel discussion

- Dimitri Schuurman, Manager Business & Domain Experts Competence Center, Imec
- Tuija Hirvikoski, Director at Laurea University of Applied Sciences
- Panagiotis Bamidis, Professor of Medical Physics and Informatics in Medical Education, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

Interactive sessions

- Silia Petronikolou, Research Associate, Lab of Medical Physics, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
- Despoina Petsani, Research Associate, Lab of Medical Physics, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
- Teemu Santonen, Principal lecturer, Laurea University of Applied Sciences

Take-home messages and closing of the event

- Despoina Petsani, Research Associate, Lab of Medical Physics, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
- Teemu Santonen, Principal lecturer, Laurea University of Applied Sciences

Annex 9 Next Door Project Conference Agenda

Envelhecimento Ativo & Cuidados ao Dependente

NEXT DOOR

Seminário

Ativar a Comunidade no Combate ao Isolamento e Solidão dos Cidadãos mais Velhos

 Agenda

Hora	Descrição
14h00 – 14h30	Registo e admissão dos participantes
14h30 – 14h45	Sessão de Abertura Joana Portugal, Vice-Presidente da <i>Aproximar</i> Miguel Silva, Presidente da <i>JF Requeixo N Sra Fátima e Nariz</i> (a confirmar)
14h45-15h00	Contributos dos ecossistemas de inovação regionais para o envelhecimento ativo e saudável Carina Dantas, <i>SHINE 2 Europe - Rede SHAFE</i>
15h00-15h15	Experiência do uso de Living Lab para o envelhecimento ativo e saudável Rosa Almeida, <i>Fundación INTRAS</i>
15h15-15h30	Metodologia de envolvimento comunitário para apoiar os cidadãos mais velhos em isolamento: da auscultação à co-criação Djamila Silva, <i>Aproximar</i>
15h30 – 15h45	Perguntas & Respostas Moderado por Ana Faria, <i>Aproximar</i>
15h45 – 16h15	Intervalo
16h15-16h30	Solidão não desejada: contributos de investigação-ação do MOAI Labs Sara Guerra, <i>Universidade de Aveiro</i>
16h30-16h45	Capacitação da comunidade: um modelo de formação-sensibilização-reflexão Susana Silva, <i>Aproximar</i>
16h45-17h00	Mobilização da comunidade para proteger os seus cidadãos mais velhos – contributos e próximos passos da iniciativa Next Door Ana Faria, <i>Aproximar</i>
17h00	Sessão de Encerramento Alexandra Rodrigues, Diretora de Serviços de Desenvolvimento Regional <i>CCDR - Centro</i>

Em parceria com:

2020-1-FR01-KA204-080560

Cofinanciado pelo Programa Erasmus+ da União Europeia

Annex 10 2nd KLID-FNF Living Lab Forum “Citizen-Driven Innovation for More Sustainable Cities” Agenda

KLID-FNF Living Lab Forum

Citizen-Driven Innovation for More Sustainable Cities

Dec 7, 2021(Tue) 07:00-10:00, CET / 15:00-18:00, KST
Ryse hotel, Seoul / Zoom Webinar

Pre-registration required.
<https://forms.gle/8RsDNRNze2nUPbhP7>
 or QR code
 Inquiry: fnfkorea@freiheit.org

TIME TABLE		
CET	07:00-07:10	OPENING ADDRESSES Jae Young Lee, President of KLID Christian Taaks, Head of FNF Korea Young Joon Song, Director of BCCEI
	07:10-08:35	SESSION 1 Moderator: Min Jung Oh, Sungkyunkwan University Presentations <i>Introduction of Living Labs from European perspective</i> Evdokimos Konstantinidis, Chairperson of ENoLL <i>Fostering Citizen Engagement: ThessAhall Living Lab for Health</i> Panos Bamidis, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki Despoina Petsani, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki <i>Living Lab for co-designing a greener city: Case of Milan</i> Israa Mahmoud, Polytechnic of Milan Discussions Hee-dae Kim, Daegu Technopark Eun-Hee Park, Goyang Industry Promotion Agency
	08:35-08:45	BREAK
	08:45-09:50	SESSION 2 Moderator: Min Jung Oh, Sungkyunkwan University Presentation <i>Increasing the Impact of Living Labs – Case of “Living Lab Handicap”</i> Benjamin Nanchen, University of Applied Science Western Switzerland Discussions Hee-dae Kim, Daegu Technopark Eun-Hee Park, Goyang Industry Promotion Agency
Co-organized by Korea Local Information Research and Development Institute (KLID) Friedrich Naumann Foundation for Freedom (FNF) Busan Center for Creative Economy and Innovation (BCCEI) European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL)		
Sponsored by Goyang Industry Promotion Agency		

Annex 11 The Poster of VITALISE Project

About

VITALISE harmonizes Living Lab procedures and opens Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in-person Transnational Access to seventeen (17) living lab research infrastructures and supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools.

Outcomes

Transnational and Virtual access to 17 Living Lab Infrastructures and Datasets

ICT tools and e-infrastructures for data, computing and networking, integrated to the European Open Science Cloud

Training activities for researchers to exploit Living Lab tools.

A Harmonization Framework for Health and Wellbeing Living Labs

Get involved

Harmonization Body

Subscribe

Open Calls for researchers

Consortium

<https://vitalise-project.eu>

[@VITALISEproject](https://twitter.com/VITALISEproject)

info@vitalise-project.eu

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[VITALISE H2020 project](https://linkedin.com/company/VITALISEproject)

Scan Here

Project coordinator: Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis, EnoLL
Scientific coordinator: Prof. Panos Bamidis, Laboratory of Medical Physics Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101007990.

Annex 12 The Brochure of VITALISE Project

Co-Creation

Health & Wellbeing Living Labs
Research Infrastructures
Academia & Researchers
Healthcare Providers
Public Institutions
Local, regional, national and European policy makers

Consortium

VITALISE
Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure

VITALISE harmonizes Living Lab procedures and opens Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond.

Get to know us!

<https://vitalise-project.eu>
info@vitalise-project.eu

...collaborate for the benefit of society.

Starting date: 1/4/2021
Project Duration: 36 months
EU contribution: € 4 999 262.50
19 partners / 11 EU countries
Project Coordinator:
Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis
Scientific Coordinator:
Prof. Panos Bamidis

Let's connect!

[@VITALISEproject](#)
[@VITALISEproject](#)
in VITALISE H2020 Project

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007990.

Transnational and Virtual Access for external researchers to seventeen (17) Living Lab infrastructures and datasets.

Three (3) open calls in March & December 2022 and May 2023.

Joint Research Activities on rehabilitation, transition in care and smart environments for active and healthy ageing.

Design and adoption of ICT tools and e-infrastructures for data, computing and networking, integrated to the EOSC.

A **Panel Management Tool** for facilitating management of scientific panels.

The **VITALISE Software Development Kit** for effective access to the infrastructure technologies.

The **VITALISE Platform** to support research and data analysis services.

The VITALISE Solution

Training of researchers to optimally exploit Living Lab tools for their research.

Summer schools for young researchers.

Online educational materials and training programmes for both staff and users of the infrastructures.

Postgraduate courses to introduce the value of living labs in the health and wellbeing domain.

An **Acceleration Bootcamp** for business modeling, go-to-market strategy, scaling, revenue model, partnering, and raise of funding.

Our Living Labs need business models that enable their sustainability beyond a project's lifecycle, optimal use of time and resources and maximum exploitation of research results from the local community.

Let's shape the future of Living Labs together!

Transnational collaboration established among and beyond the consortium partners.

The **VITALISE Starting Community**, a large thematic living lab ecosystem of virtually interconnected research infrastructures in the Health and Wellbeing domain.

A self-sustainable **Harmonization Framework** for Health and Wellbeing Living Labs to provide wider, simplified, and efficient access to Living Lab infrastructures.

A **Harmonization Board and Body** for the harmonization of Health and Wellbeing Living Labs' procedures and services.

Standards that will be open and publicly available to appeal to all Living Labs.

A **Harmonization Toolkit** to include documents about requirements, specifications, guidelines or characteristics.

Annex 13 Information Flyer for the First Open Call for TA

VITALISE
Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure

Do you want to visit a Living Lab Infrastructure to conduct your research studies?

VITALISE covers your travel & accommodation expenses to visit and conduct research studies in Living Lab infrastructures in other countries for free.

1

Introduction

Research Infrastructures act as fundamental building blocks of research and innovation, in relation to addressing imperative global societal challenges, such as health related issues and the ageing population. In this direction, **Living Labs** have emerged as resilient Research & Innovation infrastructures that have proved to be key to the integration of **Research & Innovation processes in real life settings**, focusing primarily on **people** and their engagement in research procedures. ● ● ●

2

Transnational Access

Adhering to the principles of open science and innovation, VITALISE project provides wider, simplified, and more efficient access to seventeen (17) Living Lab Research Infrastructures to researchers from multiple disciplines to conduct research studies, allowing for free mobility of researchers and flow of knowledge and technology on an international level. To this end, the project has partnered with nine (9) Living Labs from **Greece, Belgium, Spain, Austria, Hungary, Finland** and **Canada** who are accepting research proposal submissions until 9 May 2022 (results announced by 31 July 2022). ● ● ●

3

Modality of Access

Transnational Access can be either (i) fully in-person, (ii) partially remote (i.e., in-person access for a specific time period combined with remote access to the infrastructure's facilities for the rest of the unit of access) or (iii) fully remote. Transnational Access **expenses are completely covered** by the project and during in-person access researchers will receive financial support for **travel subsistence** and **daily allowance**. Researchers may only apply for Transnational Access to the Living Lab Infrastructures situated in different countries from their own. ● ● ●

4

Joint Research Activities

Researchers are encouraged to submit research proposals concerning the project's three Joint Research Activities (JRAs) on (i) **rehabilitation**, (ii) **transitional care** and (iii) **everyday living environments**, and collaborate with the project partners to conduct research studies in one of these areas. However, researchers from multiple disciplines are eligible to join (e.g., policy makers, experts in communication studies, social workers, computer/ technology scientists, psychologists, experts in sport science, pedagogues/educators, data scientists, etc.) and propose their own research studies. ● ● ●

3

Modality of Access

Transnational Access can be either (i) fully in-person, (ii) partially remote (i.e., in-person access for a specific time period combined with remote access to the infrastructure's facilities for the rest of the unit of access) or (iii) fully remote. Transnational Access **expenses are completely covered** by the project and during in-person access researchers will receive financial support for **travel subsistence** and **daily allowance**. Researchers may only apply for Transnational Access to the Living Lab Infrastructures situated in different countries from their own. ● ● ●

SCAN FOR MORE

VITALISE-PROJECT.EU

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[VITALISE Project](https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCVitaliseProject)

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Annex 14 The VITALISE Dissemination Activities Reporting Tool

VITALISE Dissemination Activities Report

Fields marked with * are mandatory. ✕

Disclaimer ✕
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* Name(s) and/or Affiliation(s)

- * Type of activity
- Organisation of a Workshop or a Networking event
 - Participation to a Workshop
 - Participation to a Conference
 - Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop (Networking events, Exhibitions, Symposia, Webinars etc.)
 - Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects (Synergies)
 - Training Session
 - Press release
 - Newsletter
 - Scientific and peer reviewed publication (article and/or papers and/or presentation)
 - Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication) (Blog entries)
 - Media Publications (News pieces, articles etc.)
 - Poster
 - Flyer
 - Social Media
 - Website
 - Video/Film
 - Other

* Title of activity / slogan

Title of the event (if applicable)

Venue (if applicable)

* Date

Title of the presentation (if applicable)

URL of the activity (if applicable)

URL of the publication (if applicable)

Type of audience reached below. Please select more than one type ONLY if applicable, up to a maximum of 3.
 Please indicate ESTIMATED no of persons reached per type of audience (EC request)

	Industry	Medical Organisations	Research Community	Policy Makers	Society (Customers, Civil groups, general public)	Media	Other
No. of persons	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Please copy below any relevant links (e.g. to videos, presentation files, announcement screenshots, etc.)

Please upload any photos relevant material (e.g. videos, presentation files, announcement screenshots, etc.)

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